

Collective and Stochastic Motion in the Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation Part II

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In a previous note (1) i.e. Part 1, we argued that the time dependent Schrodinger equation could incorporate both stochastic and collective or frame of reference motion for the case of $V(x,t)$. In particular, we examined a harmonic oscillator equation with an additional potential of $f(t)x$ and used a product wavefunction $\exp(iy\dot{b}/dt) W(y-b(t)/m)$ where $x=y+b(t)/m$ and two equations to find a solution (following (3)). The second equation yields a differential equation for $b(t)$. The spatial solution is basically that of a quantum oscillator with an origin changing in time multiplied by a phase.

In (2), a method of unitary transformations is developed to deal with $y=x+a(t)$, where $m\dot{a}(t)=b(t)$. This approach is applied to a free particle Hamiltonian with the added potential of $f(t)x$. Furthermore, (2) utilizes the momentum wavefunction in order to find a solution for which fictitious potentials in the accelerated frame cancel the potential $f(t)x$.

We argue in this note, that one may generalize the approach of (2) to a more general Hamiltonian than the free particle one, provided that $V(y+b)=V(y) + g(t)y + q(t)$. The oscillator potential satisfies this requirement. We also argue that one does not need to use Fourier transforms, but may directly obtain a spatial solution which has been shown in Part 1 (1). We compare the two results.

Unitary Transformations and a New Hamiltonian and Wavefunction (2)

In (2), a method of using unitary transformations to handle the transformation $y=x+a(t)$ is developed. A new Hamiltonian is obtained which is of the form: $H_0 + m \dot{a}/dt x + g(t)$. If the original Hamiltonian is $-1/2m d/dx d/dx + z(t)x$, then an acceleration $a(t)$ may be obtained such that $m \dot{a}/dt x$ cancels $z(t)x$. (We show in the next section that one may solve this same problem using a wavefunction $\exp(iy\dot{b}/dt) W(y-b,t)$. The difference is that one does not need to use a momentum wavefunction as is done in (2), but explicitly obtains a spatial wavefunction solution.)

The transformation considered in (2) is: $y=x+a(t)$ ((1))

The time dependent Schrodinger equation is multiplied by a unitary operator U i.e.

$U i\hbar d/dt (\text{partial } U^{-1} U W = U H U^{-1} U W$ ((2)) where

$U W(p) = \exp(i a(t)p) W(p+m\dot{a}/dt)$ ((3))

One may note that $\exp(a(t) d/dx)$ is the generator which yields $q(x+a(t)) = \exp(a(t) d/dx) q(x)$. In momentum space, it is $\exp(i a p)$ because $p=-i\hbar d/dx$.

It is shown in (2) that ((2)) becomes:

$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{(partial)} W_1 = H_1 W_1$ where

$H_1 = H_0 + m \left[x \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} + .5 \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} + a(t) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \right]$ where $H_0 = \frac{p^2}{2m}$ the free particle Hamiltonian ((4)) (H_1 is also obtained using $\frac{1}{2m} (p + m \frac{d}{dt})(p + m \frac{d}{dt})$ which follows from the transformation.

Next ((4)) is applied to the problem: $H = \frac{p^2}{2m} + x f(t)$ ((5))

The idea is to work in momentum space and have $x f(t)$ cancel with $m x \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$ in ((4)). The last two terms on the RHS of ((4)) are pure functions of time and a phase $\exp(i \int_0^t g(t_1) dt_1)$ may be introduced such that $i \frac{d}{dt}$ operating on it yields the two terms.

In momentum space ((5)) becomes: $i \frac{d}{dt} \text{(partial)} W_p = (\frac{p^2}{2m} + f(t) \frac{d}{dp}) W_p$.

If one transforms to an accelerating frame, then $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$ should cancel $f(t)$, so one has the constraint:

$$M \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} = f(t) \quad ((6))$$

For some reason, (2) takes includes the third term on the RHS of ((4)), but neglects the fourth and writes:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W_p = (\frac{p^2}{2m} + .5m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}) W_p \quad ((7))$$

Generalization of the Approach of (2)

We argue that the approach of (2) may be generalized to $H_0 = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) + f(t)x$ such that $V(y+b(t)) = V(y) + d(t) + y r(t)$. In other words, since one wishes to cancel terms in x in the approach of (2), one may have a more general potential, such as an oscillator, which supplies an extra linear x term. In such a case, $H_0 W = E_0 W$ replaces $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ and one does not need to worry about momentum space because one does not have $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$, but rather $H_0 W$ which is replaced with E_0 . Thus, the idea of unitary transformations should be able to directly yield the spatial wavefunction and not only its Fourier transform.

Alternative Approach

Consider an alternative approach (originally given in (3), but modified in (1)). We begin with an oscillator with an extra $x f(t)$ potential term:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{(partial)} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + .5k x x W + x f(t) W \quad ((8))$$

Following (3), set $y = x - b(t)/m$ and try $W(y + b(t)/m, t) \exp(i \int y db/dt)$.

Given that $y=x-b(t)/m$, this appears to also be the view from an accelerating frame (just as in the above section). The difference is that a unitary transformation is not used.

The wavefunction is of the form of W_0W_1 i.e. a product wavefunction, so two equations arise. We try to keep all pure functions of t (i.e. not multiplied by x etc) in the first equation together with a $.5ky$ term, and place linear terms in y in the second equation. We note that:

$$d/dx \rightarrow d/dy, \quad f(t)x = f(t)(y+b(t)/m) \quad .5kxx = .5k(y+b(t)/m)(y+b(t)/m)$$

$$i\partial/\partial t \exp(iy db/dt) W_a(y+b,t) = iy d/dt db/dt W_{total} + i\exp(iy db/dt) dW_a/dy db/dt + i\partial/\partial t \exp(iEt)\exp(i\int_0^t c(t_1)dt_1)W + E W_{total} \quad ((9))$$

In other words, the time pieces are $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(iy db/dt)$ and $\exp(i\int_0^t c(t_1)dt_1)$. The first is related to a bound state in the accelerated frame and the third is used to cancel $c(t)W$ where $c(t)$ is the combination of pure time pieces appearing when one uses $x=y+b(t)/m$ and from derivatives.

$$-1/2m d/dy d/dy W_{tot} + .5kxx W_{tot} + f(t)x W_{tot} =$$

$$\{-1/2m d/dy d/dy W_a + .5ky y W_a + c(t) W_a\} + \{f(t)y + kyb(t)\} \quad ((10))$$

where

$$c(t) = f(t)b(t)/m + .5kb(t)b(t)/(mm) - 1/2m (d/dy d/dy \exp(iy db/dt)) / \exp(iydb/t) \quad ((11))$$

We consider a first equation related to a time-independent Schrodinger equation for W_a with the extra $c(t)W_a$ piece, so the overall time portion is: $\exp(-iEt) \exp(i \int_0^t c(t_1)dt_1)$.

The second equation contains the rest of the pieces and allows for the cancellation of linear terms in x , just as in the accelerating frame method. Thus:

$$E W_a = -1/2m d/dy d/dy W_a + .5k y y W_a \quad \text{where } i\partial/\partial t \exp(i \int_0^t c(t_1) dt_1) \text{ cancels } c(t)W_a. \quad ((12))$$

Thus, ((12)) is an oscillator eigenvalue equation with the center changing in time because $y=x-b(t)/m$.

The second equation is:

$$iy d/dt db/dt W_{total} + i\exp(iy db/dt) dW_{tot}/dy (1/m) idb/dt = \{f(t)y + kyb(t)\} W_{total} - 1/m i db/dt dW_{total}/dy \exp(iydb/dt) \quad ((13))$$

Which reduces to: $d/dt db/dt = f(t)/m + kb(t)/m \quad ((14))$ with y not present.

Equation ((14)) is analogous to ((6)) from the accelerating frame method. One may note that ((14)) contains the extra $k b(t)$ term, but this is due to the linear y term arising from

$.5k(y+b)(y+b)$. In ((6)), the Hamiltonian is that of a free particle. Thus, the two approaches appear to be very similar if not identical, but the latter allows one to find the spatial wavefunction.

Comparison of the Two Methods

In the accelerating frame approach of (2), an expression for the time dependent momentum wavefunction is obtained. The pure time portions of this wavefunction should match the pure time dependent portions of the spatial wavefunction obtained using the second approach.

In ((7b)), there is also the pure time term: $\exp(-im/2 \int_0^t \{da/dt da/dt - 2a d/dt da/dt\} dt)$) ((15)) where $m d/dt da/dt = f(t)$

In ((11)), there is:

$$\exp(i \int_0^t f(t_1)b(t_1)/m + .5kb(t_1)b(t_1)/(mm) - 1/2m db/dt db/dt dt)) ((16))$$

Noting that: $b(t)/m = a(t)$ and $md/dt da/dt = f(t)$, ((16)) becomes:

$\exp(i \int_0^t md/dt da/dt a(t) + .5kbb/(mm) - m/2 da/dt da/dt dt)$ which is essentially the same ignoring the extra term with k because (2) uses a free particle Hamiltonian i.e. $k=0$.

One may argue that the approach of (2) pertains to a free particle H_0 and that of (1) to an oscillator H_0 , but setting $k=0$ in the oscillator result should make the two the same. The term $m/2 da/dt da/dt$ in (2) arises from:

$$U^{-1} p^2/2m U = .5 (p+mda/dt) (p+mda/dt) = p^2/2m + da/dt P + m/2 da/dt da/dt$$

It seems that the energy as seen in the accelerated frame is included in a phase factor for the momentum wavefunction in (2) i.e. $\exp(-i p^2/2m - i t da/dt p - i m/2t da/dt da/dt)$.

In the second approach, one uses $\exp(-iEt)$ where E are the oscillator energy values, but written in the accelerated frame i.e. $.5ky^2$ is used not $.5kx^2$. Thus, both approaches use energy in the accelerated frame, but the oscillator energies $\hbar\omega(n+.5)$ do not make this so evident.

The second approach has: $\exp(i (x-b(t)/m) db/dt)$ which contains a pure time piece $\exp(-i b db/dt)$ which does not seem to be present in form of (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine a method of unitary transformations applied to an accelerating frame i.e. $y=x-a(t)$ as developed in (2). This method is applied to a free particle Hamiltonian with an added $x f(t)$ potential. We argue the method may be generalized to an oscillator with an

added $x f(t)$ potential because $\frac{1}{2}k (x-b(t)/m)^2$ yields a term linear in x . We find that the two methods yield $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{da}{dt} = f(t)$ and $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{db}{dt} = f(t) + k b(t)$. If $k=0$, the two are the same i.e. $ma(t)=b(t)$. In the approach of (2), the momentum wavefunction is obtained while in the second approach the spatial wavefunction results. We find that a pure time factor is the same for both approaches. In (2), the energy in the accelerated frame is written explicitly in the $\exp(-i \text{energy } t)$ factor while in the second approach one has energy eigenvalues from the oscillator, but in the accelerated frame as one uses $y=x-b(t)$ as the position operator.

References

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